

Annual Report for Period:04/2003 - 03/2004

Submitted on: 06/21/2004

Principal Investigator: Warnick, Wendy K.

Award ID: 0101279

Organization: Arctic Research

Title:

Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program

Project Participants

Senior Personnel

Name: Warnick, Wendy

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Post-doc

Graduate Student

Undergraduate Student

Technician, Programmer

Other Participant

Research Experience for Undergraduates

Organizational Partners

Other Collaborators or Contacts

Activities and Findings

Journal Publications

Books or Other One-time Publications

Web/Internet Site

Other Specific Products

Contributions

Contributions within Discipline:

Contributions to Other Disciplines:

Contributions to Human Resource Development:

Contributions to Resources for Research and Education:

Contributions Beyond Science and Engineering:

Special Requirements

Special reporting requirements: None

Change in Objectives or Scope: None

Unobligated funds: less than 20 percent of current funds

Animal, Human Subjects, Biohazards: None

Categories for which nothing is reported:

Organizational Partners

Activities and Findings: Any Research and Education Activities

Activities and Findings: Any Findings

Activities and Findings: Any Training and Development

Activities and Findings: Any Outreach Activities

Any Journal

Any Book

Any Web/Internet Site

Any Product

Contributions: To Any within Discipline

Contributions: To Any Other Disciplines

Contributions: To Any Human Resource Development

Contributions: To Any Resources for Research and Education

Contributions: To Any Beyond Science and Engineering

**Arctic
Research
Consortium
of the
United States**

Member Institutions:

University of Alaska
Anchorage
University of Alaska
Fairbanks
University of Alaska
Statewide
Alaska North Slope Borough
Dept. of Wildlife Management
Arizona State University
Bates College
Brown University
Center for Northern Studies
University of Colorado
Cold Regions Research and
Engineering Laboratory
Dartmouth College
Desert Research Institute
Embry-Riddle
Aeronautical University
Foundation for Glacier
and Environmental Research
Iñsaġvik College
Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory
of Columbia University
Louisiana State University
Marine Biological Laboratory
Michigan State University
University of Massachusetts
Amherst
University of Miami
University of Nebraska
Lincoln
University of New Hampshire
Northern Illinois University
Ohio State University
Oregon State University
Pennsylvania State University
San Diego State University
Sandia National Laboratories
Smithsonian Institution
SRI International
Texas A&M University
University of Washington
Woods Hole
Oceanographic Institution

3535 College Road
Suite 101
Fairbanks, Alaska 99709
USA
907.474.1600
Fax: 907.474.1604
E-mail: arcus@arcus.org
<http://www.arcus.org>

18 June 2004

Simon Stephenson
Arctic Research Support and Logistics Program Manager
Office of Polar Programs, Room 755
National Science Foundation
4201 Wilson Blvd.
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Mr. Stephenson:

Attached is one copy of the 3rd Annual Report of the Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) as required in Section F-1 of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279, between the National Science Foundation and ARCUS. The report describes accomplishments for the period 1 April 2003 through 31 March 2004 and outlines projected activities for 1 April 2004 through 31 March 2005.

Included in the annual report, as specified in the Cooperative Agreement, are:

- An executive summary outlining the major activities and accomplishments during the period of this cooperative agreement;
- a narrative summary of accomplishments, future plans, and discussion of major change in direction or pace, by individual task;
- a one-page summary showing costs by five major tasks; arctic community science planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section coordination, arctic science education, information and outreach, and core support (Attachment A).
- a five-page, multi-column table, by individual activity, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the actual costs for years one and two, actual expenditures through March 2004, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for April 2004-March 2005 (Attachment B);
- a one-page, multi-column table summarizing the entire cooperative agreement by Form 1030 categories showing the currently approved five-year budget, the actual costs for years one and two, actual expenditures through March 2004, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for April 2004-March 2005 (Attachment C); and
- the proposed budget and request for \$2,287,360.00 for the period of April 2004-March 2005 on NSF Form 1030 (Attachment D).

The ARCUS board of directors and staff are very pleased with the achievements of the past year and the work we have accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF. We look forward to continuing to work with NSF and the arctic research community on these important initiatives. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

Wendy K. Warnick
Executive Director

THE ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM OF THE UNITED STATES

Third Annual Report Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279 April 2003 through March 2004

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) has undertaken a variety of activities to enhance NSF arctic research programs through Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. ARCUS has worked with the scientific community to identify new research objectives, logistical requirements, and educational activities that benefit planning and implementation of NSF-supported science initiatives in the Arctic. Specific activities have been organized under four major tasks:

1. Arctic science planning—coordinating science planning for the arctic research community at several levels, including continuing examination of logistical requirements with the goal of improved access for all researchers in the Arctic;
2. Organizational support for the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section programs, including the Arctic System Science Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program;
3. Development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
4. Information and outreach activities disseminating timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and to the public.

An additional 5th “task” is the provision of core support for ARCUS’ NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the infrastructure necessary to support this work regardless of the specific nature of activities from year-to-year.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

Accomplishments under this major task include activities to address arctic research support and logistics needs, including:

- Publishing the updated recommendations on research support and arctic logistics, providing long-term advice on arctic logistics and science support issues for the NSF Office of Polar Programs.
- Continuing development and maintenance of ALIAS, an arctic research support and logistics web site that serves as an information resource and access point for the research community.
- Working with the arctic research community, GIS experts, and NSF to convene planning meetings and provide community information resources to support research planning and analysis in the Arctic by using geospatial concepts and resources as a coordinating framework.
- Planning and coordinating the large international Open Science Meeting for the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) program.
- Supporting the development of a community science plan for the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST), a research initiative proposed for the Bering Sea.
- Initiating planning to conduct a community survey to identify data coordination and data management needs for arctic research.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

Accomplishments under this major task include a number of activities for the ARCSS Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program, as well as the development of informational posters on aspects of arctic research for the Arctic Section as a whole.

2.2 ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE (ARCSS) PROGRAM COORDINATION

Activities under this sub-task include:

- Providing organizational support to the work of the ARCSS Committee (AC).
- Coordinating discussions, planning, and implementation for changes to the structure and process of ARCSS Program community science management.
- Coordinating the ARCSS-wide synthesis effort.
- Coordinating and supporting the work of the ARCSS data advisory working group.
- Beginning implementation of an ARCSS wide-science management office.
- Publishing and distributing the proceedings of the 2002 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop.
- Coordinating and supporting a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) science management office, which included planning and convening several workshops.

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

Activities under this sub-task include:

- Planning and support for *Partnering with Arctic Communities*, which will be convened as a special session at the May 2004 Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences.
- Coordinating and supporting a community planning process to develop a social science research plan for the Bering Sea in order to establish responsible community-centered Bering Sea ecosystem research and partnerships between communities and researchers.

2. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

Activities under this major task include:

- Coordinating and managing the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to increase communication and collaborations among the dispersed arctic research community and arctic residents.
- Coordinating the 2003 virtual field expeditions for Arctic Alive!
- Planning and implementing the Teachers & Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program, an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in Arctic research as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry.

3. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

Accomplishments related to information distribution and outreach include:

- Publishing and distributing one issue of *Witness the Arctic* to over 8,800 subscribers.
- Developing and maintaining web-based resources for arctic research.
- Managing the Arctic Info listserv.
- Maintaining and expanding *The Directory of Arctic Researchers*.
- Convening the two-day *Arctic Forum*, a seminar highlighting important arctic research findings, in Arlington, VA in April 2003.

4. CORE SUPPORT

Accomplishments described in Core Support are direct project activities that benefit and support multiple NSF activities that cannot be identified with one specific project.

THE ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM OF THE UNITED STATES

3rd Annual Report

April 2003–March 2004
OPP-0101279

The narrative describes activity for the period April 2003 through March 2004, the third year of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. Accomplishments and work in progress are described through March 2004, and projected activities are indicated for the period April 2004 through March 2005.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 Arctic Research Support and Logistics

Accomplishments

- The ten-member Research Support and Logistics Working Group (RSLWG) met three times by teleconference in the past year. The teleconference discussions were held to guide the development of the report's content during a series of reviews by working group members, other invited reviewers, and community review.
- RSLWG co-chairs Terry Tucker and Peter Schlosser met with ARCUS staff twice by teleconference, to discuss progress and identify outstanding contributions needed.
- The draft report was prepared in layout with figures, maps and photographs and distributed for open community review in May 2003. The opportunity for community review of the document was publicized through ArcticInfo, other listserves, and on the ARCUS web site. Twenty-nine individuals provided comments on the draft report.
- With oversight by the working group, ARCUS staff revised the draft report in response to comments received and distributed a new draft for review by the working group and invited reviewers in August 2003.
- Key partners and collaborators included the 10-member working group and the reviewers who provided comments on the draft report. An additional 35 people were asked to provide specific material for the report, including VECO Polar Resources and NSF staff.
- The report provides guidance for investments in physical infrastructure and other resources to broadly benefit the arctic research community in the coming decade.
- 2000 copies of the final report, *Arctic Research Support and Logistics: Strategies and Recommendations for System-Scale Studies in a Changing Environment*, were printed in October 2003. Copies of the report were available at the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, AGU Fall Meeting, and other relevant Arctic-focused meetings.
- Approximately 1,000 copies have been distributed to-date in response to requests or to identified individuals and organizations. The report is available as a PDF download on the ARCUS web site.

Projected Activities

- Continue distribution of hard copies and availability of on-line edition.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Follow on activities regarding community planning for logistics needs is under discussion among the working group chairs, NSF program officers, and ARCUS leadership. Major recommendations of the report include establishment and support of a panel to guide development of an arctic observing network.

1.2 Logistics Internet Resources; Arctic Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS)

Accomplishments

Data Expansion

- Added 19 field sites to database, for a current total of 43. Field site information includes: site manager contact information, logistics support providers, permitting requirements, access issues, information about available resources at the site, links to other resources, and other site information.
- Added 9 vessel entries to database for a current total of 28. Vessel information includes ownership and management, physical characteristics (including performance capability), onboard scientific equipment and space, communications and data equipment available, and other vessel information.
- Developed online graphical display of 27 research vessel cruises in arctic waters. Information is searchable by year, location, vessel name, and research project or initiative, and results appear as track lines on a polar projection map. Cruise tracks are linked to cruise descriptions, vessel information, project websites and lead scientist contact information.

Increased Functionality

- Added additional data fields recommended by managers and users for vessel and cruise track information and improved categorization and searchability with new structural fields in the database.
- Added a database-driven vessels page as an additional type of information; the database can automatically display vessel records grouped according to user-selected criteria such as nationality or capability.
- Interconnected ALIAS with VECO Polar Resources database and the ARCUS Directory of Arctic Researchers through the use of dynamic links, which perform a search of an off-site database and directly display the results.
- Redesigned the website index for quicker access and updated it to include all resources currently available on the site.
- Improved the client input interface to speed the process of data input.

Community Coordination and Outreach

- Convened an advisory group to provide guidance in expanding vessel data information and functionality. The advisory group is composed of representatives from the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO) and the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB) and represents a variety of international arctic research organizations:
 - » *Martin Bergmann, Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Canada*
 - » *Sara Bowden, Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB)*
 - » *Dieter Fütterer, Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Sciences (AWI)*
 - » *Anders Karlqvist, Swedish Polar Research Secretariat*
 - » *Mike Prince, University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS)*
 - » *Tom Pyle, Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB)*
 - » *Odd Rogne, International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)*
 - » *Simon Stephenson, Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO)*

- ARCUS staff gave oral and poster presentations at relevant workshops and conferences to increase and improve collaborations. These include:
 - » SEARCH Open Science Meeting, Seattle, Washington
 - » North Slope GIS Meeting, Seattle, Washington
 - » Circumarctic GIS Meeting, Seattle, Washington
 - » 2003 AAAS Arctic Science Conference 2003
- Continued collaboration with VECO Polar Resources (VPR); as the logistics contractor for NSF-funded arctic research, VPR continues to be an important partner with ALIAS in data sharing, planning, and coordination.
- Increased communication and coordination with UNOLS Arctic Icebreaker Coordinating Committee (AICC) through attendance of AICC meeting and agreement of ALIAS representation of all future meetings, with the goal of improving vessel information in ALIAS.

Projected Activities

- Convene an eight to ten member advisory working group to guide the overall development of ALIAS. Members will include representatives of entities that contribute to or use ALIAS, or whose development should have close developmental goals and interconnections. The composition of the advisory group will be developed in agreement with NSF arctic logistic support managers.
- Make the vessels section a more useful tool for international collaboration and planning. With the help of the vessels advisory group, develop and implement a strategy for obtaining scheduling information and design an accessible, user-friendly format for the presentation of information about the scheduling of research vessels and opportunities for collaboration on future research cruises. The goal is to have scheduling process descriptions and cruise tracks for the major icebreakers, estimated to be approximately 12, online in 2004.
- Expand site and record information, with a goal of reaching 100 records from the current 71, with emphasis on terrestrial research stations and vessels in Russia.
- Strengthen collaboration and coordination with logistics-related organizations, data collection efforts, and related initiatives, such as GIS development and the CEON initiative, through formal presentations at relevant meetings, working group discussions, informal connections, and soliciting input from users and providers of logistics data.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace:

In the first half of this year, work on ALIAS was focused on expansion – increasing the number of resources listed. In the latter part of the year, at the request of the vessel advisory group and NSF, significant effort was devoted to expanding the vessel and cruise track database and very little work was done on other aspects of ALIAS. While ALIAS was conceived to serve researchers, particularly those developing a new project or proposal, it has also been seen as a useful tool for the arctic research community as a whole, to encourage and assist collaboration and planning across national boundaries among resource managers, agencies, and international organizations. Examples range from quickly accessing the email address of a site manager in another country, to international collaboration on the planning of an icebreaker research cruise.

1.3 Planning for Integrated Arctic Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

The Arctic GIS activities described here, the North Slope GIS meeting, Arctic GIS Planning meeting, and development of the Arctic GIS website and Discussion Forum, represent a significant step toward advancing research planning and analysis in the Arctic by using geospatial concepts and resources as a coordinating framework.

Accomplishments

- Worked with meeting organizers to convene a North Slope GIS Meeting in Seattle, Washington in October 2003 in order to survey and discuss GIS efforts with respect to research and logistics support on the North Slope of Alaska. Worked with meeting chair Allison Graves of Nuna Technologies to arrange meeting logistics, technical requirements and prepare participant materials. Staffed the 20-person meeting.
- Worked with meeting organizers to convene an Arctic GIS Planning meeting in Seattle, Washington in November 2003 in order discuss important next steps in implementing improvements to Arctic Geospatial Information Infrastructure (Arctic GII). Arranged meeting logistics, technical requirements, and prepare participant materials. Staffed the 31-person meeting.
- Worked with the Arctic GIS community and NSF to develop an Arctic GIS Website to reflect recent developments in Arctic GII and to provide the arctic GIS community with information and services to facilitate development of a coordinated Arctic GII. The website includes:
 - » Introduction and background information on Arctic GIS and GII themes and developments
 - » Information and summaries of NSF-sponsored Arctic GIS meetings
 - » Several pages of annotated weblinks relevant to Arctic GII
 - » News and Events page
 - » Discussion Forum – an on-line bulletin board to foster discussion and collaboration within the community of GIS professionals, arctic scientists, resource managers, data providers and the wider community on issues related to Arctic Geospatial Information Infrastructure (AGII). The Forum includes open-ended user-defined discussion threads, as well as providing an avenue for moderated thematic discussions.
- Sent draft Arctic GIS Website to various Arctic GIS researchers and professionals for comment and input January 2004.
- Published Arctic GIS Website February 2004 and engaged in significant outreach activities in order to inform and engage researchers and GIS professionals regarding website development; published announcements via ArcticInfo and ARCUS website.
- Hosted a teleconference January 2004 to survey and coordinate plans for proposed Arctic GIS projects in support of logistics; worked with teleconference organizer Allison Graves to coordinate technical, logistic, and content issues of the teleconference.

Projected Activities

- Continue development of Arctic GIS Website and Online Discussion Forum:
 - » Add content and products to the website as determined by NSF and Arctic GIS community.

- » Further develop the Online Discussion Forum and hold targeted thematic discussions to advance GII efforts; work with NSF and Arctic GIS community to select forum topics and moderators.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

1.4a-b Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination and Planning

ARCUS organized and facilitated the first Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Open Science Meeting (OSM), held 27–30 October 2003 in Seattle, Washington, at which researchers from around the world presented and discussed evidence of rapid environmental change in the Arctic. SEARCH is an interagency effort to understand the causes, connections, and consequences of recent arctic environmental changes, emphasizing their interactions with global climate change and potential impacts on the biosphere, including human social and economic well-being. At the Open Science Meeting, over 440 social and natural scientists, policy makers, and stakeholders from 18 countries explored the basic premise of SEARCH—that a complex of interrelated changes is occurring across arctic terrestrial, oceanic, atmospheric, and human systems. A major goal of the OSM was to assist SEARCH in developing cooperative relationships with many of the pertinent arctic science programs sponsored by other nations and international groups. Other goals were to encourage scientists from a range of disciplines to share evidence of environmental change in the Arctic, identify results from individual research projects that could inform the overall SEARCH objectives, and contribute to the SEARCH program either through linking their ongoing work to this program or through the design of new projects. The description of activities below covers cooperative agreement activities 1.4a (SEARCH OSM Coordination and Planning— related primarily to the open science meeting) and 1.4b (SEARCH OSM Student Scholarship Program). Projected Activities describes the activities related to a transition of the SEARCH science management function and support for the science steering committee’s work to ARCUS.

Accomplishments

- Worked with 10-person Organizing Committee (OC) to develop program focus and structure of SEARCH Open Science Meeting (OSM) to provide an international forum to present and discuss research on arctic environmental changes occurring across terrestrial, oceanic, atmospheric, and human systems.
- Worked with SEARCH OSM OC to formulate a draft agenda, which was circulated to the SEARCH Science Steering Committee, representatives from the Interagency Working Group (IWG), and the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) for comment and input in April and May 2003. The agenda included a combination of invited keynote talks, panel discussions, parallel science sessions with contributed talks, and poster sessions.
- Distributed conference announcements via ArcticInfo, ARCUS website, and via hardcopy at various conferences and meetings, including a call for input and suggestions, calls for presentation and poster abstracts, and registration and logistics announcements.

- Created a SEARCH OSM poster for outreach purposes; presented poster at the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) Arctic Science Conference meeting in Fairbanks, Alaska.
- Recruited and invited speakers, panelists, and science session co-chairs; the invited contributors included 21 keynote speakers, 13 panelists and 16 co-chairs from a variety of universities, research institutes, government agencies, and indigenous organizations.
- Facilitated the development of the parallel science sessions by working with the OSM OC and the 16 science session co-chairs to compile submitted abstracts and guide the abstract selection process.
- Convened science session co-chair teleconferences and worked with the co-chairs to recruit speakers and develop final parallel science session agendas, which included 76 contributed talks on a wide range of geographic, disciplinary, and thematic foci.
- Worked with over two-dozen arctic researchers, conference center staff and hotels to coordinate the planning of 23 associated meetings that were held in conjunction with the SEARCH OSM. These side meetings represented a variety of topical, organizational, and disciplinary foci, and ranged from small groups holding working meetings on an arctic science issue to larger town meetings held to gather input on international programs.
- Developed a SEARCH Open Science Meeting website. Prepared and maintained content including agenda, registration, abstract, side meeting and general logistics information.
- Developed and tracked on-line registration process; added credit card payment capability.
- Developed, edited, and maintained online searchable database of submitted oral and poster abstracts.
- Worked with NSF publications office and other arctic organizations and programs to gather outreach and informational materials for display at the conference.
- Worked with the OSM Organizing Committee, and media liaisons from NSF, University of Washington, and NASA to engage print, radio, and Internet media and to arrange a press event held at the conference; significant press interest and several stories resulted.
- Arranged and paid for travel and accommodations for keynote speakers and other key participants, including select student scholarship recipients.
- Prepared final meeting materials including agenda, venue and travel information, participant list, preliminary abstracts; provided information via website and participant notebooks with CD-ROM.
- Coordinated all logistic and technical requirements for the conference with conference center and hotels; worked with the telecommunications company Vision Net, Inc., to provide press event and plenary sessions to public via streaming video.
- Managed the conference activities and provided staff support for the 4-day conference of 454 participants and 23 associated side meetings. Participants represented 177 organizations from 18 countries equaling 19% international (non-U.S.) participation.
- Developed and published on the website post-meeting materials and information, including final agenda, abstracts, powerpoint presentations, participant list, compilation of media coverage, and edited video of the sessions.
- Worked with science session co-chairs and Organizing Committee to prepare the final conference proceedings, including an introductory executive summary, summary of the parallel science sessions, full abstracts, and participant list.
- Developed and administered merit-based student scholarship program to encourage the participation of young investigators; funded some portion of participation costs for 38

undergraduate and graduate students representing 21 institutions and 5 countries; students represented over one dozen scientific disciplines, including anthropology, biology, ecology, economics, hydrology, geography, geophysics, and natural resource management.

- Managed student poster contest, including the development of judging criteria, selection of judges, and presentation of poster contest results at the conference. ARCUS partnered with the Arctic Institute of North America (AINA) to offer awards to the three competition winners. The winners will receive support to attend a relevant conference on the Arctic and their work will be highlighted at the 2004 Arctic Forum in Washington DC. They also will receive a two-year Arctic Institute of North America membership, which includes a subscription to the interdisciplinary journal *ARCTIC*.
- ARCUS also worked with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC) to insure participation of Alaska Native students; 5 Alaskan Native students were sponsored.

Projected Activities

SEARCH Open Science Meeting Follow-Up

- Complete and distribute SEARCH Open Science Meeting proceedings in Summer 2004.

SEARCH Program Activities

- Work with NSF Program Manager, SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) Chair and committee members, and the current Science Management Office (SMO) to transition website activities to ARCUS, including re-design and development, hosting, and maintenance; planned for Winter 2004/2005
- Work with NSF Program Manager, SEARCH SSC chair and committee members, current SMO, and the SEARCH Interagency Working Group to plan and implement the gradual transition of other SMO activities during the upcoming year, including:
 - » Supporting the identification of research and organizational priorities;
 - » Developing processes for community input and development;
 - » Workshop and conference organization and planning;
 - » Supporting scientific program planning and implementation;
 - » Coordination with the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC);
 - » Coordination with other related programs (CLIVAR, ASOF, CEON, etc.); and
 - » Public outreach and education efforts.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

There were significant changes in pace of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting due to the increase in interest and participation beyond original planning and expectations. The SEARCH OSM was originally planned for 300 participants. As participants continued to register, the decision was made by the SEARCH Steering Committee to accommodate as many participants as possible. Over 440 people participated in the meeting and 23 side meetings were organized, which increased the overall meeting support costs. In addition, ARCUS was asked by the SEARCH OSM organizing committee to develop a student scholarship program to ensure the rigorous and productive participation of young investigators in the SEARCH OSM, which was not included in the original scope or budget. Following the SEARCH OSM, and with the changing leadership of the SEARCH Science Steering Committee, ARCUS was asked to transition toward responsibility for a SEARCH science management office and support for the Science Steering Committee.

1.5 Planning for Bering Sea Research: Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST)

The NSF Arctic Sciences Section is supporting a planning process to initiate collaborative studies of the sub-arctic seas, culminating in cooperative ecological research of the eastern, western and basin areas by Japan, Russia and the United States. The planning process began with the *Ecosystem Studies of the Sub-arctic Seas* workshop in September 2002, after which a nineteen-member working group was formed to begin development of a draft science plan. ARCUS was tasked to coordinate the March 2003 meeting of the working group, to provide staff support for the development of the science plan, and to publish and distribute the plan when completed.

Accomplishments

- Planned and coordinated the three-day, 23 participant workshop in March 2003. Key collaborators and partners include the 23 workshop participants, representing 11 academic institutions, agencies (NOAA, NMFS, ADFG), local residents, and Japanese and Russian institutions.
- Posted follow-up information on the ARCUS web site after the workshop, including PDF and Powerpoint downloads of all the presentations, timeline, writing assignments, and draft contributions.
- Coordinated with working group members to develop and complete writing assignments.
- Prepared the first draft science plan; distributed it for working group review in July 2003.
- Revised and distributed draft science plan for open community review in October 2003. The opportunity for community review of the document was publicized through ArcticInfo, other listserves, and on the ARCUS web site. Comments were received from 11 individuals.
- Planned and convened a BEST town meeting session during the SEARCH Open Science Meeting in October 2003. Approximately 30 participants attended and provided comments on the draft science plan.
- Assisted in planning for BEST town meetings at AGU Fall meeting in December 2003, AGU Ocean Sciences meeting in January 2004, the ASLO/TOS meeting in February 2004, and the 2004 AAAS meeting.
- Revised draft science plan in response to comments received during the community review and town meeting. Distributed penultimate draft for working group review in February and March 2004.
- Solicited invited reviews from individuals with key expertise.

Projected Activities

- Revise the draft science plan in response to comments received from the working group and invited reviews.
- Work collaboratively and in support of chair, Dr. George Hunt, to prepare the science plan in its final form for publication.
- Publish and distribute the science plan in July 2004.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

1.6 Workshop, to be determined

Accomplishments

- No activities in the past year.

Projected Activities

- No activities are planned in the coming year.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

1.7 Revision and Reprinting of the SEARCH Brochure

Accomplishments

- There were no activities in this project during the past year.

Projected Activities

- No further activities are planned in the near-term, although we receive many requests for the brochure and copies are no longer available.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

1.8 Community Survey to Identify Arctic Research Data Coordination and Data Management Needs

A clear need has emerged through a number of Arctic planning activities, conferences and meetings for better information about needs and problems in data coordination and data management for Arctic research in general, and specifically for projects and programs that are inter-disciplinary, multi-institutional, international in scope, or interagency. ARCUS proposed to conduct a community survey using the online survey system that we have developed.

Accomplishments

- The survey tool has been designed and the online survey process is ready to be launched.

Projected Activities

- A small advisory group will be convened to guide the community survey process, analysis, summarization, and distribution.
- The survey will be launched in Fall 2004 and continue for several months.
- The information submitted by the research community about arctic research coordination and data management needs will be compiled, analyzed, summarized, and distributed to the various organizations and projects for which it will be useful.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

We expected to launch this survey in March 2004 but have delayed the process pending the opportunity to discuss the needs and the focus of the survey more thoroughly with NSF program managers.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Accomplishments

- At the request of the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, ARCUS produced an information and outreach poster, *Arctic Science Discoveries*, which described Arctic Sciences Sections activities and programs.
- Developed and produced laminated copies of *Arctic Science Discoveries* for use in the NSF Office of Polar Programs (OPP) informational display.
- ARCUS has provided additional copies of large format, laminated copies of the poster to NSF, as well as small format glossy versions for outreach purposes.
- *Arctic Science Discoveries* was first displayed at the Fall Meeting of AGU in December 2002, and has been displayed since at many relevant workshops and conferences.
- A PDF was provided to facilitate future printing.
- Developed a poster on arctic science education activities sponsored by the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, for inclusion in the NSF OPP informational display and display at various relevant meetings and conferences.
- Dr. Robert Wharton, OPP Executive Officer, first displayed the education poster at the Fall Meeting of AGU in 2003 to support his presentation on education and outreach programs. It has since been presented at a number of Arctic meetings and workshops.
- Extra laminated copies have been provided to NSF for additional display along with a PDF to facilitate future printing.
- Prepared the design concept for an Arctic Sciences Section brochure, at the request of NSF staff.

Projected Activities

- Work with NSF education and outreach staff to develop the content and complete an informational brochure on arctic research supported by the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, important findings, and relevant programs and activities.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.2 ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE (ARCSS) PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination

Accomplishments

- Reviewed the composition of the ARCSS Committee (AC) with the AC chair and the NSF Program Director in the context of new priorities and the representations of key programs and disciplinary perspectives and expertise.

- Selected and appointed new members to replace members due to rotate off the committee.
- Worked with ARCSS Committee chair to prepare materials for teleconference and in-person meetings of the 11-member AC to assess the direction of the ARCSS Program, research priorities, new planning underway, the current funding picture, and important opportunities.
- Provided the committee chair with a stipend and travel funds to participate in ARCSS-related meetings and workshops. Provided travel support for members of the ARCSS Committee to attend committee and ARCSS-related meetings.
- Organized and staffed an ARCSS *ad hoc* data committee meeting in Boulder, Colorado in May 2003. The data committee was appointed by the ARCSS Committee and charged with gathering information from the ARCSS Data Coordination Center and the Joint Office for Science Support about the current state of data collection and archiving in the ARCSS Program. The *ad hoc* committee included scientists representing a variety of arctic research disciplines, especially those that are doing data-intensive research or with unusual requirements for data management, coordination, or archiving. The committee generated a report for the ARCSS Committee and the NSF ARCSS Program Manager that highlights the major issues related to ARCSS data. This report, and the information gathered during this meeting, is expected to inform the planning for the next ARCSS Science Plan and the future needs and goals of the ARCSS Program.
- Convened the first ARCSS Synthesis Retreat in Big Sky, Montana 10-16 August 2003. The retreat was designed as a small, focused effort to begin assembling a synthesized system perspective of the Arctic, its components and processes, and the linkages between these components and processes. The retreat was envisioned as more of an intellectual exercise than a program planning effort, and was expected to result in one or more scholarly papers, with hopes of forging intellectual breakthroughs in understanding how the Arctic works as an integrated system – including humans. This effort was also a first major step towards producing the next NSF ARCSS Five-Year Science Plan. Twenty-six invited scientists participated in the Synthesis Retreat, representing approximately 20 different scientific disciplines.
- In preparation for the ARCSS Synthesis Retreat, ARCUS collected a list of 20 "key readings" (articles or chapters) from members of the ARCSS Committee. The readings were collected and bound together with annotations of each. This volume constituted the essential reading in preparation for the synthesis retreat.
- ARCUS staff worked with the ARCSS Committee chair to prepare a keynote talk based on the discussions at the synthesis retreat for presentation at the SEARCH Open Science Meeting in Seattle, Washington in October 2003. This presentation is also being used as the basis for a scholarly paper that is currently in process.
- Organized and convened an ARCSS Committee meeting in conjunction with the SEARCH Open Science Meeting in October 2003. The Committee met primarily to follow-up on synthesis activities and to begin planning for a meeting in February 2004, convened to begin drafting the next ARCSS Science Plan.
- Organized and convened an ARCSS Committee meeting in February 2004 in Boulder, Colorado. The primary tasks of the meeting were to:
 - » Check the progress of the writing group tasked with drafting the scientific article that will be a major outcome of the synthesis retreat.

- » Begin planning for the second ARCSS Synthesis Retreat in Summer 2004, including appointing a planning committee for the retreat.
- » Outline the next ARCSS Science Plan, including a plan for implementation.
- » Address the needs for ARCSS data management and coordination.
- » Plan a more centralized programmatic structure and a process for establishing ARCSS research priorities, encouraging and supporting community involvement in science planning, supporting the ARCSS Committee's AC work, and coordinating community involvement in the ARCSS Program.
- Prepared a summary review of science management and project support activities of the various Science Management Offices (SMO) and Science Project Offices (SPO) supported by the ARCSS program, based on information provided by the SMOs and SPOs for the February 2004 AC meeting.

Projected activities:

- Expand ARCSS coordination and ARCSS Committee support to encompass a centralized ARCSS Science Management Office.
- Provide staff support and coordination for the approximately monthly ARCSS Committee teleconferences.
- Organize, convene, and provide staff support for the second ARCSS Synthesis Retreat at Granlibakken Conference Center at Lake Tahoe in August 2004.
- Facilitate the development of products that emerge from the second ARCSS Synthesis Retreat, including working with AC members to prepare a scholarly paper on the process of synthesis.
- Provide staff support, a stipend and travel funds to support the work of the ARCSS Data Advisory Working Group chair. Convene and support a meeting of the ARCSS Data Advisory Working Group in Summer 2004.
- Organize and support a face-to-face ARCSS Committee meeting in Fall 2004.
- Work with the ARCSS Committee to develop several publications to support ARCSS program outreach and community involvement, including a newsletter and an updated ARCSS brochure.
- Develop and manage tools and processes to encourage and facilitate research community involvement in all levels of idea development, science planning, and implementation of ARCSS research efforts. Support up to three ARCSS "Interdisciplinary Node" meetings (~10 people at each).
- Research and analyze existing ARCSS Program websites and integrate crucial information, features, and functionality from all of them into one expanded ARCSS Program web site.
- Provide support for a scaled-down Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) science support and community development function through a subcontract.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The intensified work of the ARCSS Committee and the initiation of the ARCSS synthesis process, along with the changes in the ARCSS Program science management structure, have required additional coordination, communication, planning, and production of information during the past year. These activities do not constitute a change in direction but the level of activity has somewhat increased. A dramatic increase in the level and intensity of support activities is expected in the coming year, commensurate with the

transition to operating a large-scale science management and coordination function for the ARCSS Program.

2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop 2002

The ARCSS All-Hands Workshop, held in February 2002, brought together approximately 300 researchers, 75 of whom were students, representing a wide array of natural, social, and physical sciences to discuss the current state of knowledge about the arctic system and to look toward the future of arctic system research. The workshop provided an excellent forum for sharing research, exchanging ideas, and interacting with researchers from disparate disciplines.

Accomplishments

- Published and distributed the proceedings from the 2002 ARCSS All-Hands workshop. The proceedings include eleven oral presentation abstracts, 173 poster abstracts, a summary of the recommendations from each working group, and the ARCSS Committee's analysis and synthesis of recommendations for further planning and implementation of ARCSS Program priorities.
- 1500 copies of the proceedings were printed and distributed. A downloadable PDF of the publication is available on the ARCUS web site.

Projected Activities

None

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.2.3 Coordinating a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) Science Management Office

Accomplishments:

- Organized and supported a Lessons in Integrated Analysis of Human Dimensions Research Workshop in May 2003. Although this small workshop was funded primarily through another grant source (the NSF Biocomplexity in the Environment program), it received a small amount of staff support through the cooperative agreement SMO funds and clearly contributed to the overall HARC development effort. Outcomes of this workshop include:
 - » A HARC synthesis paper (Huntington, Hamilton, Nicolson, Voinov, Ogilvie, in preparation)
 - » A report on HARC SMO activities and plans for 2003-2004, which was submitted to the NSF ARCSS and Arctic Social Science program managers in June 2003. This report includes *Experiences in Synthesis*, a white paper prepared and offered to ARCSS Committee as a contribution to the ARCSS synthesis effort, and another white paper, *Suggestions for Improving the Preparation and Review of Interdisciplinary Proposals*.
- Organized and supported the 2-day HARC Patterns, Connections, and Methods Workshop, held in Seattle, Washington in conjunction with the SEARCH Open Science Meeting in October 2003. This open workshop included presentations and posters from

HARC PIs as well as others doing integrative human/environment interactions research both within and outside of the Arctic. A ten-member organizing committee was recruited to plan the workshop, after which the committee continued to function as the HARC science steering committee.

- The workshop included 99 participants, including 22 students (both graduate and undergraduate). Several Alaska Native elders attended, as well as representatives from several Alaska state, Canadian and U.S. federal agencies.
- ARCUS partnered with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC) to entrain several Alaska Native students. Two of the ANSC commissioners attended as well.
- Prepared a workshop report summarizing the abstracts, discussions and recommendations. The report will be distributed to workshop participants and made available on HARC website as a PDF.
- Convened a ten-member HARC science steering committee representing diverse research disciplines and human dimensions expertise to provide vision and guidance to the HARC program.
- Prepared a poster on the Huntington, *et al.* HARC synthesis paper to be presented at the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA) Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS V) in May 2004.
- Facilitated and coordinated the preparation of a special issue of the journal *ARCTIC*, which will be published in late 2004. Solicited contributions from funded HARC researchers, most of which were submitted and reviewed in the past year.
- Significant updates were made to the HARC web site in the past year. The interface style and functions were redesigned, as well as the presentation of materials and information, to allow for more efficient navigation and accessibility. Pertinent information regarding HARC funding and research initiatives was added or updated.

Projected Activities:

- None

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Participants at the HARC/Biocomplexity in the Environment: Coupled Human and Natural Systems Workshop held in November 2002 and the Integrated Analysis Workshop held in May 2003 strongly recommended an open community workshop to assess research methods and common patterns and connections within the field of human dimensions research in the Arctic. These recommendations, combined with the need to integrate social sciences and human dimensions research fully into the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, led to the Patterns, Connections, and Methods workshop in October 2003, just prior to the SEARCH OSM. The organizational and staff support, participant support costs, and meeting support costs associated with this workshop had not been included in the program plan or budget previously.

2.2.4 Preparation and publication of CHAMP: *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*

Accomplishments

- Ongoing distribution of the report electronically via the ARCUS web site.

Projected Activities

- Continue to distribute the report via the ARCUS web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination and Planning

Accomplishments

- Discussed overall focus, goals, and timing with the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager and initiated planning in collaboration with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC) for a workshop on *Partnering with Arctic Communities*, to be held as a two-day special session at the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS-V) in May 2004.
- The *Partnering* workshop goal is to highlight the best practices in the field and demonstrate to young researchers how to conduct respectful, cooperative research in arctic communities, or in any community. The workshop will directly affect the 50 or 60 people who will attend, and since it will be held in conjunction with ICASS V, which attracts approximately 300 social scientists, many more researchers are expected to hear about the workshop.
- Selected and convened, in collaboration with the ANSC, an organizing committee representative of circumarctic indigenous peoples and arctic social scientists to plan *Partnering with Arctic Communities*.
- Worked with the committee to identify workshop goals, format, location, agenda, as well as the timeline, main topics, keynote speakers, and invited participants.
- Announced the conference and publish a call for abstracts.
- Invited selected presenters and participants and arranged travel and logistics.
- Supported a subcontract with the University of Alaska Fairbanks to provide staff support for the preliminary planning and coordination of the ICASS V to be held in Fairbanks, Alaska in May 2004.

Projected Activities

- Develop the final *Partnering with Arctic Communities* agenda; provide staff support for the workshop in May 2004.
- Work with the Alaska Native Science Commission, the NSF Arctic Social Sciences program manager, and the *Partnering* workshop participants to plan and produce whatever post-workshop products are agreed upon.

- Publish and distribute a second edition of *Arctic Social Sciences: Opportunities in Arctic Research*, a publication which is frequently requested by researchers and which is also used in many arctic social sciences courses.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The NSF Arctic Social Sciences program manager asked ARCUS and the ANSC in October 2003 to postpone the workshop and to hold it in conjunction with the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences in May 2004 to reach a broader audience and to expand the opportunities for participation from young researchers and international participants.

2.3.2 Translation and publication of *Den Nye Sikkerhed - Groenland I Et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* (The New Security: Greenland in a Security Political Perspective)

Accomplishments

- Ongoing distribution of *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* at meetings, workshops, and by request.

Projected Activities

- Continue to distribute *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* at meetings, workshops, and by request.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.3.3 Preparation and Publication of *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change*

Accomplishments

- Sold or distributed all 1,500 copies of *Earth is Faster Now*, and so commissioned a second printing using the proceeds from book sales.
- Displayed the *Earth is Faster Now poster* at a number of arctic meetings and workshops, including the ARCUS 15th Annual Meeting and *Arctic Forum*, at the AAAS Arctic Science Conference in September 2003, at the AGU Fall Meeting, and at other venues.
- Co-editor Igor Krupnik attended the 7th Polar Meteorology conference in Hyannis, Massachusetts in May 2003 to present a poster on the *Earth Is Faster Now*, to bring the volume to the attention of physical scientists and other researchers who might otherwise consider this work irrelevant to their research. The poster was ranked as No.1 for the poster session, highly unusual for a poster on a topic outside of the research normally presented at this major meeting.

Projected Activities

- Hold a book signing and reception at the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences in May 2004.
- Continue marketing and distribution.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.3.4 Humans in the Bering Sea Ecosystem Community Planning

A group representing arctic social scientists and resident communities of the Bering Sea has initiated a community planning process to develop a social science research plan for the Bering Sea, with support from the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program. The goal of this plan is to establish responsible community-centered Bering Sea ecosystem research and partnerships between communities and researchers. The plan will be developed to serve the interests of the resident communities of the Bering Sea and to provide a model process for future collaborative research with Native communities. Towards that end, ARCUS was asked by the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager to assist in the organization and outreach activities related to science plan development.

Accomplishments

- Worked with 3-member steering committee and the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager to convene the Bering Sea Ecosystem Community Forum in Anchorage, Alaska in March 2004. The goal of the Community Forum was to explore community research interests, to plan ways to collect a broader range of community priorities, and to discuss the possible shape of the research plan.
- Arranged meeting logistics, participant materials, and staffed the 27-person workshop; participants included local residents, elders, representatives of native and local natural resource associations, social scientists, and other representatives of programs and projects centered on Bering Sea ecosystem.

Projected Activities

- Work with the steering committee to create an informational flyer for the “Humans and the Bering Ecosystem Town Meeting” to be held during the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Scientists (ICASS V) in May 2004.
- ARCUS will continue to support the planning process and the community development of the science plan if recommended and requested by the steering committee and workshop participants.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

ARCUS’ education programs have been developed around several guiding principles that have been formulated over the past twelve years through several community workshops, our work with the researchers, educators, students, and with residents of the Arctic. These principles are:

- Education programs must be relevant, inquiry-based, and, if focused on K-12, they should align with National Science Education Standards.
- Education efforts should build on existing education efforts; the community should focus on increased collaborations between established programs and networks, and should build supportive partnerships between researchers, educators and schools, and communities.

- Arctic residents must be involved in developing and implementing educational programs and outreach, and effective partnerships must be promoted and nurtured.
- There is a need for increased awareness or “visibility” of the arctic region and its residents, the unique and analogous aspects of the Arctic as a polar region, and its role in the Earth system.

All of the ARCUS education programs fit into this context and are developed to:

- Ensure that high-quality information and education in arctic science is available to the general public, students and teachers, and Natives of the Arctic.
- Enable interested and talented students to pursue scientific careers in the Arctic.
- Ensure that the scientific and technical workforce exists to meet the challenges of the arctic research agenda.

In the past year, no activities were undertaken in the general education category, 3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities. All activities fit within three projects: The Arctic Visiting Speakers’ Series, Arctic Alive!, and Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC).

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

Accomplishments

- No activities were undertaken in this general education category.

Projected Activities

- None.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers’ Series

ARCUS implemented an Arctic Visiting Speakers’ (AVS) Series in January 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents.

Accomplishments

- Eight speakers participated in the Series in the past year, addressing arctic issues at 35 different public engagements. Speakers presented at a variety of public venues including libraries, classrooms, and on the radio, as well as at graduate seminars and conferences.
- Roughly 760 people attended the public presentations.
- Of the eight speakers, two speakers traveled from other countries to speak in the U.S.; Two U.S. speakers traveled to other countries. Four U.S. speakers visited institutions within the U.S.
- The topics covered included: Inuit culture, Saami knife-making and handicrafts, arctic politics and subsistence, native health, snow and climate change, arctic languages, Inuit art (i.e. baleen basket making, drumming, singing, and Inuit film making.)

- The Speaker's Bureau was updated and currently has 40 profiles for potential Arctic Visiting Speakers.
- An Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series brochure was developed for distribution at conferences and meetings.
- The Arctic Visiting Speakers Series' web site was revised and updated and includes all the presentations by year as well as "current tours."

Projected Activities

- Continue to promote the use of the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to facilitate collaboration and information sharing about arctic research and the Arctic, including distribution of information via Arctic Info and *Witness the Arctic*.
- Advertise the AVS series more extensively among Arctic residents; encourage participation by indigenous experts as visiting speakers and by Arctic communities as host institutions.
- Post the AVS information to several educational list serves around the country to stimulate interest from the K-12 education community to apply as host institutions.
- Support up to ten speaker tours in the next year.
- Continue to recruit individuals for the Speakers Bureau, although host institutions are not restricted to inviting speakers from the Speakers' Bureau.
- Post updated information about speaker tours on the ARCUS web site, including presentation videos and other materials sent to ARCUS by host institutions and speakers.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3.3 Arctic Science Education Report

Accomplishments

- All print copies of the report have been distributed but we continue to receive many requests for it. The report is available electronically on the ARCUS web site.

Projected Activities

- Continue to make the report available electronically.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3.3 ARCTIC ALIVE!

In September 2001, ARCUS was awarded funding through the National Science Foundation – Directorate for Geosciences, to develop and implement a pilot distance-delivery education program. Arctic Alive! allows students to “participate” in arctic research without leaving their classrooms. This program is based on a very successful program developed by Heurisko Ltd. in New Zealand called LEARNZ. Through Arctic Alive! students interact with researchers in remote arctic locations by using a variety of technologies. Using these technologies and corresponding curriculum, classrooms can simultaneously investigate the

Arctic, discover careers in science, and research this unique and exciting world right along with the experts. Arctic Alive! continued in 2003 and was partially funded through the cooperative agreement.

Accomplishments:

- An Arctic Alive! brochure was created to provide information about the program. The brochure has been widely distributed at a number of arctic conferences and workshops as well as at several national science education conferences. It is also available electronically on the Arctic Alive! web site.
- A new section was developed on the Arctic Alive! web site for the 2003-2004 expeditions and revisions were made to the site design for a more efficient and navigable presentation of materials.
- Three Arctic Alive! field expeditions were implemented in the past year:
 - 2003 Ecological Change Expedition:* The 2003 expedition was based out of Kotzebue, Alaska, in April 2003. This expedition focused on ecological change in Kotzebue Sound. The research used Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) and Scientific Ecological Knowledge (SEK) to develop an ecological profile of the nearshore benthic ecosystem in Kotzebue Sound. Teachers had access to educational materials and activities as well as archived live and online interaction with a middle-school science teacher, Amie Foster, lead researcher, Lisa Clough, and other members of the research team and the community. Amie Foster was also a Teacher Experiencing Antarctica and Arctic (TEA) participant.
 - 2003 Snow Science:* Snow Science took place in March and April of 2003 out of Kotzebue, Alaska. Researcher Merrick Johnston and team skied 400-miles through Northwest Alaska. Merrick's research objective was to determine how storm tracks affect contaminant loading in Northwest Alaska and to evaluate how this may vary with inter-annual weather patterns. With assistance from local students, members of the research team dug snow pits, collected snow samples, and interviewed elders along the way. Merrick posted journal entries, photos, and responded to student questions as she traveled from village to village.
 - 2003-2004 Eider Journey:* Eider Journey is a two-part expedition. The first part took place in September 2003 in Cold Bay, Alaska. The second part will take place in the late spring or fall of 2004. Eider Journey is an education and outreach program centered on issues related to conservation and management of Alaska's threatened Steller's eider population and the nearshore marine habitats on the Alaska Peninsula and eastern Aleutian Islands. The program is a partnership between the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, the Alaska North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management, the North Slope Borough School District, the National Science Foundation Office of Polar Programs, and ARCUS. High school students from Barrow, Alaska work with biologists in both the eider's nesting and wintering areas, to develop an increased understanding of the needs of this species and the threats it faces. In the fall of 2003, 4 high school students traveled to Cold Bay to collect eelgrass samples and band eiders.

Projected Activities:

- ARCUS is collaborating with other agencies and organizations as a means of integrating and expanding the scope of Arctic Alive!
- Elements of Arctic Alive! have been incorporated into *TREC - Teachers & Researchers*

Exploring and Collaborating (TREC), an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in Arctic research, working closely with scientists, as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry.

- The Arctic Alive! concepts and framework have been incorporated into two proposed projects:
 - » *Strengthening STEM Teaching & Learning through Arctic Connections* provides strategies to remedy disconnections between STEM teacher preparation and teaching practice through the development, facilitation, and study of a multifaceted professional development program. It targets mid-career K-12 teachers and employs online seminars, hands-on experiences, symposiums, and digital learning libraries.
 - » *Live from the Arctic*, a collaborative project designed to provide a suite of Arctic-focused education and outreach opportunities for the 2007 International Polar Year.

3.5 Teachers and Researchers – Exploring and Collaborating (TREC)

The Teachers & Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program is an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in Arctic research, working closely with scientists, as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry. Participating TREC teachers serve as a conduit for reciprocal exchange of experience and knowledge between researchers and educators, and as a foundation for a growing community of students, educators, researchers, community members, and the general public that is engaged in science teaching and learning. Through TREC, teachers will have the opportunity to increase their knowledge, enhance teaching skills, transfer their experiences to the classroom, engage in leadership roles, and develop a supportive network of colleagues. TREC extends beyond field experiences to encompass collaborative learning among teachers, students, researchers and communities through Internet-based communications. Virtual campfire chats, online journals, message boards and photo albums, curriculum development, classroom activities, and “webinars”—online, real-time, seminars broadcast live—reach a wide audience to share experiences and expertise towards the invigoration of science education and student inquiry.

TREC activities began in January 2004 and included the initial planning and launch of the TREC program, the development of a TREC web site, the application and selection and matching process for teachers and researchers, and the teacher and researcher orientation process, accomplished through a series of webinars. Additional activities will be continued into the next cooperative agreement year. Accomplishments thus far are listed below.

Accomplishments

- Convened a management group in partnership with VECO Polar Resources and worked with management group to determine scope of program, program planning components, and task scheduling.
- Developed program materials, including program description and participation requirements for teachers and researchers; announced program via Arctic Info, ARCUS website, and education listservs.
- Developed and launched TREC website, which includes program information, participation requirements, online application process, weblinks, and structure for program participants to interact online.

- Designed and implemented application process for teachers and researchers.
- Convened selection committee to select teachers and researchers from applicant pool.
- Selected and matched teachers and researchers for the 2004 field season.
- Selected and developed tools to facilitate the online collaboration between teachers, researchers, and the community, including webinars (real-time seminars broadcast over the Internet), bulletin board forums, chat capabilities, file sharing workspace, on-line calendar and field journals.
- Developed content for the orientation webinars and conducted four orientation webinars for participating teachers and researchers.

Projected Activities

- Convene advisory committee to assist in program, content, and curriculum development.
- Conduct an additional orientation webinar, focused on the development of educational resources and curriculum materials for participating teachers and researchers.
- Implement the formative evaluation process to gather information about the application process, selection, accessibility, content, and ease of use, involvement of underserved populations, and outreach to arctic residents. Additionally the evaluation process will assess TREC's overall impact on science education. In addition to questions about the application and selection process, the efficacy of online resources for orientation and training, and the support provided through the program, the evaluation process assesses:
 - » Do the project experiences/components facilitate increased, lasting interaction and collaboration between the arctic research community, arctic residents, and TREC teachers?
 - » Do participating teachers increase their understanding of arctic research?
 - » Do participating teachers increase their teaching ability and their resources for classroom teaching?
 - » Does this experience lead to increased learning among the students of participating TREC teachers?
 - » Do the collaborative partnerships successfully produce a database of learning objects and activities that can be readily used by other teachers facilitating introduction of arctic research into classrooms of teachers who did not participate in a field research experience?
- Continue the development of the TREC web site to support teacher interactions, online journaling and photo albums, information about the TREC research projects, and the development of the TREC learning resources database.
- Coordinate and support teacher and research project interactions and planning prior to the field portion of the TREC experience.
- Coordinate and support TREC teacher deployment to the field and their ongoing communications with other educators, students and classrooms, and the public.
- Implement the Arctic Science Education Listerve.
- Implement the Virtual Campfire Chat program as TREC teachers and researchers return from their field research experiences.
- Organize and convene the Arctic Learning Symposium at the conclusion of the first year of TREC, a combination face-to-face and virtual conference where TREC teachers and researchers will share what they have learned from the experience, work together to integrate learning resources and curriculum materials developed during the year, and

provide information to potential TREC participants and any individuals interested in using information developed through the TREC program.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 *Witness the Arctic*: Chronicles of the NSF Arctic Sciences Program

Accomplishments

- Published and distributed 10,000 copies of *Witness the Arctic* (Spring 2004, Volume 11, Number 1). This issue is a 32-page newsletter with a feature story that provides an overview of October 2003 SEARCH Open Science Meeting. The newsletter also includes a four-page insert on arctic research at Desert Research Institute.
- *Witness the Arctic* currently has approximately 8,800 subscribers, 3,300 outside the U.S.
- This issue contains material from approximately 60 contributors, including academic researchers, program managers, agency personnel, educators, and facility managers, both U.S. and international.
- Published on-line editions of the newsletter on ARCUS' web site, <http://www.arcus.org>.

Projected Activities

- Prepare and publish the Autumn 2004 issue of *Witness* (Volume 11, Number 2), with distribution anticipated in October 2004.
- Begin work on the Spring 2005 issue of *Witness* (Volume 12, Number 1), with publication planned for May 2005.
- Publish on-line edition of the new issues of the newsletter on the ARCUS' web site, <http://www.arcus.org>.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Because of the timing of information to be submitted for *Witness*, including for the feature article on the SEARCH Open Science Meeting and on the synthesis effort and programmatic changes in the ARCSS Program, the editors decided to omit the planned Autumn 2003 issue of *Witness the Arctic* and combine the content into one newsletter, the Spring 2004 issue.

4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources

The ARCUS web site provides essential information and resources for the very diverse and geographically distributed Arctic research community and now serves over 6,000 files from over 2,000 pages. Data and information is dynamically served from external 4D and MySQL databases and the site features dynamic, user created content through simple interfaces - message boards and forums, photo albums, and calendars. It is the focal point for web-served programs such as Arctic Alive! and TREC, and provides important information to the research community about key activities, meetings and programs, including the ARCSS Program, developments in Arctic GIS, and information about the SEARCH Open Science Meeting. Among many other resources, the web site provides program information, electronic copies of publications, agenda, abstracts, and participant lists from key arctic meetings, and

audio and video archives from a variety of programs and meetings. The ARCUS web site provides information for the general public about arctic research, a forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers, approaches for integrating arctic research with educational programs, access to other researchers, programs, and stakeholders working in the Arctic, viable ways to inform and involve arctic residents in research activities, and information about progress and recommendations related to various arctic research initiatives.

Accomplishments

- A whole-site search interface has been completed and is ready for implementation. The interface will be implemented in conjunction with a major site redesign of both style and functionality that is now underway.
- The development of a MySQL database on the ARCUS server in the past year allowed the use of open-source PHP scripted bulletin boards. We now have multiple instances of interactive bulletin boards being used to support such programs as the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, Arctic GIS, Arctic Alive!, and TREC.
- Updated and added web forms, which allow users to register for workshops, subscribe to newsletters and lists, apply for participation in programs, submit Calendar information, and submit surveys. These updates and additions have resulted in more flexible user interactions with site information and easier management of the information submitted.
- Redesigned several major sections of the web site to update program information and to improve search functions, information delivery, and ease of information management. Most of the web site improvements for specific projects are discussed in the relevant project activity description in this report.
- Initiated a major project to insert appropriate “alt tags” into every page and function of the web site in order to conform to federal accessibility standards.
- Created, maintained, and updated sections of the web site for ARCUS-facilitated programs, meetings, and workshops described in other activity descriptions in this report.
- Posted draft reports related to arctic research activities, making them available for community review.
- Posted on-line versions of various arctic research publications, including all documents prepared by ARCUS, for easy access and downloading.
- Provided links to numerous other arctic organizations’ research sites, databases, planning processes, and other information of interest to the arctic research community.

Projected Activities

- Further development of dynamic tools (PHP, MySQL and 4D webservices)
- Implement the major redesign of the web site, now in progress, to improve site appearance, accessibility, search functions, information delivery, and ease of content development, management, and delivery.
- Complete the alt tagging and accessibility modifications for all existing pages.
- Continue to maintain, manage, and update the large, dynamic, and high-traffic web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.3 Arctic Info Listserve

Accomplishments

- Received, reviewed, accepted or declined, edited and formatted over 450 submissions for the Arctic Info listserv in the past year. Announcements include notices such as publication announcements, PhD openings, and international conference announcements.
- Communicated with subscribers regarding postings, special information requests, non-automated subscribe or unsubscribe requests, and other concerns.
- Maintained a database of subscribers in order to track subscriptions and unsubscribes, and to analyze use and areas of interest.
- Managed the “bounce list” by researching bounced posts to correct and update addresses, investigate apparently dead domains, and delete consistently bouncing addresses from the subscriber list.
- Provided general information on the demographics of the subscriber list to several organizations and individuals interested in using the list to announce information to the research community.
- Distributed 348 Arctic Info messages from April 2003 to March 2004, with an average of 25 announcements per month.
- The listserv has had 467 new subscribers since April 2003, resulting in 4,304 current subscribers.
- There have been 1565 posts from Arctic Info since its creation in September of 1996. Each year has seen an increase in submissions for distribution and in subscribers.
- During the past year a new list moderator and secondary editor were trained to manage Arctic Info.
- A large increase in both submissions and subscribers to Arctic Info occurred after the October 2003 SEARCH meeting.

Projected Activities

- Continue advertising, maintenance, and management of the listserv.
- Switch from current listserv software to a more flexible, user friendly, and less anxiety provoking list management software.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.4 The Directory of Arctic Researchers

Accomplishments

- Added 276 new records between April 2003 and March 2004. As of March 2004, there were a total of 3,904 individual records in the Directory.
- Surveyed researchers with current directory records to get updated contact and current research information.
- Surveyed significant international research organizations and individuals to expand non-U.S. researcher records in the database.
- Maintained and regularly updated a downloadable PDF of the Directory including alphabetically-listed individual researcher entries and a cross-reference file listing

researchers by name within science specialty categories. Developed a new Directory PDF design and creation process, which streamlined the PDF creation and makes a smaller document and smaller electronic file size.

Projected Activities

- Develop and populate a new directory section for educators, which includes identifying individuals and groups for inclusion, sending survey forms, updating individual records for the database, and developing new search features on the Directory web site.
- Implement an automated daily update of the online Directory, which will include an automated daily Directory PDF creation and uploading process.
- Develop web services to allow interactions (pulling and pushing information) with other arctic databases such as the CEON-IMS, Barrow Area Information Database-Internet Map Server, and the VECO Polar Resources ARLSS project database.
- Continue maintenance and expansion of the on-line directory.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.5 Internet Graphics Archive

Accomplishments

- Development of the Internet Graphics Archive was on hiatus in the past year to reallocate staff resources to ALIAS research and data entry and preparing for and staffing the SEARCH Open Science Meeting.

Projected Activities

- Continue to organize, and categorize the large ARCUS collection of arctic-related images. Continue research and data entry of relevant information about source, subject, dates, research project, and funding source for all of the images.
- Obtain use permissions and attribution for the entire ARCUS image collection.
- Prepare the online interface to make images available while protecting copyrights and requiring attribution for any resources used.
- Refine the online graphic and image archive search capabilities.
- Identify or produce additional figures, cartoons, photographs, and maps depicting arctic research-related information and make this information available through the archive on the ARCUS web site.
- Continue to develop short abstracts that explain each graphic simply and clearly and that provide information necessary for attribution, as well as citations for source material and other related references.
- Continue developing contracts with providers to define legal use of photos and figures.
- Make graphics available for downloading and printing from the ARCUS web site through a searchable database and PDF format.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Very little work was accomplished on the archive in the past year because of the need to reallocate staff resources for ALIAS research and data entry and preparing for and staffing the SEARCH Open Science Meeting.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

Accomplishments

- Planned and hosted a two-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 15th Annual Meeting in Arlington, VA in April 2003; attended by 121 participants, including arctic researchers from the U.S. and other countries, policy makers, federal agency personnel, and arctic residents.
- The Forum was chaired by Dr. Igor Krupnik of the Smithsonian Institution's Arctic Studies Center and Dr. F. Stuart Chapin from the University of Alaska Fairbanks, and focused on the topic *Responding to Global Change: Resilience and Vulnerability in the Arctic System*. Keynotes included presentations by James Mahoney, Director of the U.S. Climate Change Science Program; Igor Krupnik and Aron Crowell of the Smithsonian's Arctic Studies Center; and the four student winners of the ARCUS Award for Arctic Research Excellence. The *Forum* also featured a panel discussion, moderated by Dr. Daniel Mann from the University of Alaska Fairbanks, on how the challenges posed by global change will be met by society. Panel members included two Alaska Native representatives, a Northern Region staff from the U.S. Bureau of Land Management, and the Consul General of Canada.
- The *Arctic Forum 2003* featured 19 oral presentations and 31 posters. Information was presented on research funded by NSF, arctic research supported by other federal agencies or programs, and significant international arctic research efforts.
- ARCUS staff participated or sponsored Arctic outreach activities at the September 2003 AAAS Arctic Science Conference, at the Fall Meeting of AGU in 2003, at the National Science Teachers Association Conference in 2004, at Coalition for National Science Funding sessions throughout the year, at the National Science Teachers Association Conference, and at other relevant meetings and workshops.
- ARCUS also developed information resources regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities and participated in outreach activities at scientific meetings and workshops to inform the broader scientific community and key policy and decisions-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings.

Projected Activities

- Publish and distribute the 2003 *Arctic Forum* abstract volume.
- Convene a two-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 16th Annual Meeting in Washington, DC in May 2004. The focus of the *Arctic Forum 2004* will be *Recent Decrease of the Arctic Sea Ice: Its Causes, Consequences, and Historical Perspective*. The 2004 *Arctic Forum* will be chaired by Dr. Wieslaw Maslowski of the Naval Postgraduate School and Dr. Mark Serreze of the Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences (CIRES) at the University of Colorado Boulder.
- Print and distribute the *Arctic Forum 2004* abstract volume.

- Prepare posters or presentations on request and participate in major scientific meetings or workshops to provide information and outreach regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.7 Publication: *The Arctic*

A need has long existed for a publication that introduces the environments and peoples of the Arctic and is scientifically accurate and relevant while remaining comprehensible to the general public, including middle and high school students. To address this need, ARCUS began developing an overview of the arctic region for a general audience in 2001, with funding through the previous cooperative agreement with NSF. Tentatively titled *The Arctic: Changes in a Polar Region*, this book is similar to a magazine in the quality of graphics and level of complexity and will be accessible to a wide range of readers. The contents and the publication design and layout are targeted to the general public and middle and high school students. The contents cover ocean, terrestrial, and human components of the Arctic and review various aspects of these domains, including contemporary and historical research, through a seasonal framework. Links among important arctic processes and between the biophysical systems and human cultures are illustrated.

Accomplishments

- Conducted an invited review by several arctic experts and solicited feedback and information pertinent to several important sections of the publication.
- Further work on this publication was delayed due to the high demand for staff resources to be dedicated to other projects, primarily the SEARCH Open Science Meeting and the development of the Bering Ecosystem Study science planning process.

Projected Activities

- Research and purchase photo rights for photos selected for the final publication.
- Prepare final versions of special graphics for publication.
- Publish in December 2004 and make the initial print run of 5,000 copies available for public information requests and educational uses. The publication also will be available electronically via the ARCUS web site.
- ARCUS plans to market this publication so that additional copies can be printed upon demand without securing additional funding from NSF.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Completion of this publication was postponed to the fourth year of the cooperative agreement in order to direct staff resources to other more urgently needed projects.

4.8 Eider Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin

Accomplishments

- None in the past year.

Projected Activities

- None expected at this time.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

5. Core Support

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support the overall tasks and the projects and activities included in each task of the cooperative agreement. This category was initiated to insure stability and continuity of the direct activities that support the whole of the cooperative agreement so they are not vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year through the agreement.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization and the Executive Director is intimately involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the cooperative agreement. She is directly involved in working with outside committees and contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning, programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and project activities. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual program plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of NSF activities and projects, it is more difficult to allocate much of this time specifically to any one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct overarching management and infrastructure costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure (computer hardware and software required to maintain the network and server needed to support the database and listserv, NSF sponsored tasks), high-speed Internet, and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the Arctic research community under the cooperative agreement.

Accomplishments

- Coordinated planning, managed emerging priorities, and supervised work on all the tasks and project activities described in this report. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category.
- Upgraded hardware, software, and programming to expand capability for projects that require expanded server, network, and database capacity, support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information distribution.
- Managed the server setup, the network, the creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category. System upgrades included:
 - » All forms on the web server were converted to the built-in Flexmail engine allowing a more tightly integrated package for form creation and the end to reliance on third-party applications and plug-ins.
 - » Multiple online Bulletin Boards were developed using the open-source phpBB software utilizing the built-in PHP features of WebStar 5 combined with an installed MySQL database backend.
 - » Credit card processing was added to the web server, including a shopping cart system, a credit card processing system, and a web-based order form. This system can be used for purchasing publications online in addition to providing online meeting registration including payment processing.
 - » A completely revamped FTP server was added to the web server providing a feature increase over the formerly used built-in FTP capabilities of WebStar 5. The Rumpus FTP Server 3.3 provides better user logging, enhanced user capability settings, and much needed support for client applications requiring a fully UNIX compatible FTP server.
 - » A built-in "web crawler" or searching system was developed allowing for highly accurate full-site searches of the ARCUS web site. This feature has yet to be implemented for the end-user but the feature is ready to be used in the next site-wide redesign and overhaul.
 - » Updated the email server to the vastly superior 4D Mail system. The new features in 4D Mail allowed for much improved spam filtering routines by utilizing a tiered system of Automated IP Deny Tables, "Poison" Addresses, Keyword Denial, and DNS Blacklisting. The email server upgrades and enhanced filtering have reduced spam on the ARCUS server to near-zero levels. The system includes capability for active virus scanning and quarantining of all messages coming through the server.
 - » Remote administration of the 4D Mail server is vastly improved.
 - » 4D Mail also includes a WebMail application, which allows for remote checking and receiving of all ARCUS mail accounts (which include TREC teacher accounts) remotely.
 - » Updated the system Backup server to accommodate the increased space needs of the growing ARCUS programs.
- Supported staff training to increase technical expertise for managing the dynamic and automated portions of the web site and databases.

- Supported staff travel to arctic research meetings and workshops that addressed topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which were not specific to one project.

Projected Activities

- Coordinate planning, prioritization and supervision of work on all the tasks and projects described in the projected activities, the program plan and budget for 2004-2005. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Continue to research and upgrade hardware, software and programming required to expand the interactive and dynamic capabilities of such projects as ALIAS, the ARCSS Program SMO, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, Arctic Info, the Calendar, the Internet Graphics Archive, interactive real-time online seminars and meetings, interactive bulletin boards, meeting registration and abstract submission, streamed audio and video content, and general information.
- Manage the server setup, network, creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to direct activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Support staff participation at arctic research meetings and workshops on topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which are not specific to one project.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over twelve years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents, which reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this program plan support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and provide information and support for the conduct of Arctic research and therefore will contribute to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research supported by the National Science Foundation.

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
OPP-0101279
Total Costs by Category

Attachment A

6/18/04 15:38

	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 3 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 4 Budget
1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING						
1.1 Arctic Logistics	204,019	19,067	23,874	53,130	(24,111)	3,298
1.2 ALIAS Website	614,336	96,470	128,701	140,337	3,410	143,686
1.3 GIS Planning	73,683	35,461	100	14,240	(2,387)	23,882
1.4a SEARCH Planning	372,541	-	6,298	307,034	1,918	59,210
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support	28,776	-	-	28,776	(0)	-
1.5 Bering Sea Planning	114,844	-	32,877	70,016	(24,351)	11,951
1.6 Workshop TBD	69,097	-	-	-	-	-
1.7 SEARCH Brochure	5,741	5,741	-	-	-	-
1.8 Arctic Data Survey	10,407	-	-	1,335	3,665	9,072
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,493,446	156,738	191,850	614,869	(41,857)	251,099
Indirect Costs	628,754	65,922	77,557	257,380	(10,985)	107,973
TOTAL	2,122,200	222,660	269,407	872,249	(52,842)	359,072
2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION						
2.1 <i>Arctic Section Science Materials</i>	18,964	7,040	2,805	1,083	1	8,036
2.2 <i>ARCSS Program Coordination</i>						
2.2.1 ARCSSCoordination	1,079,042	30,274	117,883	239,688	8,259	643,372
2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop	312,570	259,825	42,447	3,226	(3,226)	-
2.2.3 HARC SMO	172,844	44,449	29,400	98,995	(26,264)	-
2.2.4 Arctic Hydrology Report	18,276	18,276	-	-	-	-
SubTotal 2.2 Direct Costs	1,582,732	352,824	189,730	341,909	(21,232)	643,372
2.3 <i>ASSP Program Coordination</i>						
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Planning	90,448	6,466	7,856	73,426	(8,546)	2,700
2.3.2 Greenland Book	12,263	12,263	-	-	-	-
2.3.3 Arctic Social Sciences Volume	40,059	15,933	23,171	954	(954)	-
2.3.4 Bering Sea Community Planning	30,325	-	-	-	-	30,325
SubTotal 2.3 Direct Costs	173,094	34,662	31,027	74,381	(9,501)	33,025
Sub-Total Direct Costs	1,774,790	394,525	223,562	417,374	(30,732)	684,432
Indirect Costs	641,979	165,313	77,974	121,549	21,137	253,536
TOTAL	2,416,769	559,838	301,537	538,923	(9,595)	937,969
3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION						
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	34,627	10,847	7,999	(0)	0	-
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers Program	143,468	37,130	21,671	24,064	3,843	24,459
3.3 Arctic Science Education Report	22,919	7,691	15,228	-	-	-
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE!	27,996	-	-	27,996	(22)	-
3.5 TREC	87,103	-	-	36,291	(2,574)	50,813
SubTotal Direct Costs	316,114	55,668	44,898	88,350	1,247	75,271
Indirect Costs	133,813	23,410	18,550	37,157	1,370	32,367
TOTAL	449,926	79,079	63,448	125,508	2,618	107,638
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH						
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter	349,294	53,943	84,978	46,540	41,980	100,025
4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources	372,661	68,740	54,936	89,307	(26,013)	87,912
4.3 Arctic Info Listserver	90,220	12,508	12,286	20,013	(3,161)	19,980
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	57,445	8,087	17,428	9,319	(1,548)	13,030
4.5 Internet Graphics Archive	60,273	-	13,734	424	26,338	27,241
4.6 Community Outreach	243,897	46,871	53,802	50,480	(4,524)	48,053
4.7 Publication: The Arctic	54,344	619	55	-	40,042	53,671
4.8 Endangered Species Bulletin	2,617	2,150	468	-	-	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,230,750	192,917	237,686	216,084	73,114	349,912
Indirect Costs	519,315	81,074	97,269	89,825	32,381	150,462
TOTAL	1,750,065	273,991	334,956	305,908	105,495	500,374
5 CORE SUPPORT						
Core Support						
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,416,150	262,598	223,309	276,243	19,321	321,505
Indirect Costs	596,820	110,337	90,618	114,646	12,447	138,247
TOTAL	2,012,970	372,935	313,927	390,889	31,768	459,752
TOTAL COSTS	8,751,930	1,508,501	1,283,274	2,233,476	77,445	2,364,805

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
OPP-0101279
NSF Task & Activity Summary

Attachment B

6/18/04 15:43

	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 3 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 4 Budget
1 Arctic Community Science Planning						
1.1 ARCTIC LOGISTICS						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	99,008	9,479	20,457	31,822	(19,212)	3,098
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	14,573	4,127	2,077	1,761	1,443	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	37,532	2,634	604	-	3,807	-
Other Direct Costs	52,906	2,828	736	19,547	(10,149)	200
Total direct costs	204,019	19,067	23,874	53,130	(24,111)	3,298
Indirect Costs	86,020	8,016	9,696	21,889	(9,411)	1,418
Total direct and indirect costs	290,039	27,083	33,570	75,019	(33,522)	4,716
1.2 ALIAS WEBSITE						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	428,260	60,048	80,628	101,646	(119)	97,416
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	72,663	14,437	14,164	11,272	4,748	16,270
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	1,254	-	1,254	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	112,160	21,985	32,656	27,419	(1,219)	30,000
Total direct costs	614,336	96,470	128,701	140,337	3,410	143,686
Indirect Costs	256,898	40,532	52,311	57,058	4,753	61,785
Total direct and indirect costs	871,234	137,002	181,012	197,396	8,162	205,471
1.3 GIS PLANNING						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	46,484	20,920	-	4,936	(1,739)	20,628
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	5,548	2,294	-	-	-	3,254
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	9,688	8,050	-	1,638	(5)	-
Other Direct Costs	11,962	4,196	100	7,666	(643)	-
Total direct costs	73,683	35,461	100	14,240	(2,387)	23,882
Indirect Costs	31,328	14,954	40	6,065	(969)	10,269
Total direct and indirect costs	105,011	50,415	140	20,306	(3,356)	34,151
1.4a SEARCH PLANNING						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	110,316	-	729	79,131	8,257	30,456
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	22,808	-	3,312	16,241	(2,378)	3,254
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	44,405	-	225	44,180	2,256	-
Other Direct Costs	195,012	-	2,031	167,481	(6,216)	25,500
Total direct costs	372,541	-	6,298	307,034	1,918	59,210
Indirect Costs	158,148	-	2,493	130,194	2,655	25,460
Total direct and indirect costs	530,689	-	8,791	437,228	4,573	84,670
1.4b SEARCH OSM STUDENT SUPPORT						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	27,945	-	-	27,945	(0)	-
Other Direct Costs	831	-	-	831	0	-
Total direct costs	28,776	-	-	28,776	(0)	-
Indirect Costs	12,374	-	-	12,374	(0)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	41,150	-	-	41,150	(0)	-
1.5 BERING SEA PLANNING						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	38,948	-	3,919	26,078	2,985	8,951
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	7,917	-	8,205	(288)	1,890	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	28,038	-	19,749	8,288	(8,288)	-
Other Direct Costs	39,942	-	1,004	35,938	(20,938)	3,000
Total direct costs	114,844	-	32,877	70,016	(24,351)	11,951
Indirect Costs	47,380	-	13,016	29,225	(9,589)	5,139
Total direct and indirect costs	162,224	-	45,894	99,241	(33,940)	17,090
1.6 WKSP TBD						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	19,368	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,304	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	32,975	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,450	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	69,097	-	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	29,712	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	98,809	-	-	-	-	-

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
OPP-0101279
NSF Task & Activity Summary

Attachment B

6/18/04 15:43

	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 3 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 4 Budget
1.7 SEARCH BROCHURE						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,090	1,090	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,652	4,652	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	5,741	5,741	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	2,420	2,420	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	8,161	8,161	-	-	-	-

1.8 ARCTIC DATA SURVEY						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	9,307	-	-	235	(235)	9,072
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,100	-	-	1,100	3,900	-
Total direct costs	10,407	-	-	1,335	3,665	9,072
Indirect Costs	4,475	-	-	574	1,576	3,901
Total direct and indirect costs	14,883	-	-	1,910	5,240	12,973

2 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination

2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,141	6,799	1,597	210	0	4,536
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	5,823	241	1,208	874	0	3,500
Total direct costs	18,964	7,040	2,805	1,083	1	8,036
Indirect Costs	7,949	2,947	1,110	435	31	3,455
Total direct and indirect costs	26,912	9,987	3,915	1,519	31	11,491

2.2 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1 ARCSS COORDINATION

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	313,405	9,127	23,970	41,862	10,112	224,303
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	76,395	4,244	12,718	24,364	(13,150)	29,286
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	307,511	10,677	29,379	56,955	47,325	186,200
Other Direct Costs	381,731	6,226	51,816	116,507	(36,028)	203,583
Total direct costs	1,079,042	30,274	117,883	239,688	8,259	643,372
Indirect Costs	372,122	12,681	34,847	68,149	14,899	235,880
Total direct and indirect costs	1,451,165	42,955	152,730	307,837	23,157	879,252

2.2.2 ARCSS ALL-HANDS WORKSHOP

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	79,144	46,331	23,683	2,059	(2,059)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	16,887	17,182	(294)	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	90,513	89,230	1,284	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	126,025	107,083	17,775	1,167	(1,167)	-
Total direct costs	312,570	259,825	42,447	3,226	(3,226)	-
Indirect Costs	130,340	108,766	17,257	1,277	(1,277)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	442,910	368,591	59,704	4,504	(4,504)	-

2.2.3 HARC SMO

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	47,167	20,151	6,780	20,236	(5,089)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,643	1,249	953	4,441	1,967	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	29,846	1,686	3,891	24,269	(12,341)	-
Other Direct Costs	89,187	21,363	17,776	50,049	(10,801)	-
Total direct costs	172,844	44,449	29,400	98,995	(26,264)	-
Indirect Costs	72,079	18,656	11,971	41,453	(10,178)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	244,923	63,105	41,370	140,448	(36,443)	-

2.2.4 ARCTIC HYDROLOGY REPORT

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,279	16,279	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,997	1,997	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	18,276	18,276	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	7,696	7,696	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	25,972	25,972	-	-	-	-

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
OPP-0101279
NSF Task & Activity Summary

Attachment B

6/18/04 15:43

	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 3 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 4 Budget
2.3 ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION						
2.3.1 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES WORKSHOP						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	22,437	6,166	4,001	9,570	5,631	2,700
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,308	46	3,241	3,021	183	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	4,798	-	-	4,798	26,927	-
Other Direct Costs	56,904	254	614	56,037	(41,287)	-
Total direct costs	90,448	6,466	7,856	73,426	(8,546)	2,700
Indirect Costs	16,858	2,727	3,113	9,857	18,041	1,161
Total direct and indirect costs	107,306	9,192	10,969	83,283	9,495	3,861
2.3.2 GREENLAND BOOK						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,326	1,326	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	10,937	10,937	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	12,263	12,263	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	5,172	5,172	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	17,435	17,435	-	-	-	-
2.3.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES VOLUME						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	8,211	2,733	5,371	107	(107)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,556	-	1,556	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	2,838	-	2,380	458	(458)	-
Other Direct Costs	27,455	13,200	13,865	390	(390)	-
Total direct costs	40,059	15,933	23,171	954	(954)	-
Indirect Costs	16,722	6,668	9,676	378	(378)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	56,781	22,601	32,848	1,332	(1,332)	-
2.3.4 BERING SEA COMMUNITY PLANNING						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	12,902	-	-	-	-	12,902
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	14,000	-	-	-	-	14,000
Other Direct Costs	3,423	-	-	-	-	3,423
Total direct costs	30,325	-	-	-	-	30,325
Indirect Costs	13,040	-	-	-	-	13,040
Total direct and indirect costs	43,365	-	-	-	-	43,365
3 Arctic Science Education						
3.1 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,694	8,181	7,290	(0)	0	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	4,043	739	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	4,505	-	548	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	7,386	1,927	161	-	-	-
Total direct costs	34,627	10,847	7,999	(0)	0	-
Indirect Costs	14,561	4,561	3,280	(65)	65	-
Total direct and indirect costs	49,189	15,408	11,279	(65)	65	-
3.2 ARCTIC VISITING SPEAKERS PROGRAM						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	41,706	9,599	8,353	8,251	(144)	9,059
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	101,208	27,301	13,195	15,612	4,188	15,400
Other Direct Costs	554	230	123	201	(201)	-
Total direct costs	143,468	37,130	21,671	24,064	3,843	24,459
Indirect Costs	60,558	15,611	8,897	9,991	2,009	10,517
Total direct and indirect costs	204,026	52,741	30,568	34,055	5,852	34,976
3.3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION REPORT						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	9,849	7,691	2,158	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,070	-	13,070	-	-	-
Total direct costs	22,919	7,691	15,228	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	9,611	3,239	6,373	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	32,531	10,930	21,601	-	-	-

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
 OPP-0101279
 NSF Task & Activity Summary

Attachment B

6/18/04 15:43

	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 3 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 4 Budget
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,053	-	-	18,053	2,367	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	4,774	-	-	4,774	(1,570)	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	3,762	-	-	3,762	(3,762)	-
Other Direct Costs	1,407	-	-	1,407	2,943	-
Total direct costs	27,996	-	-	27,996	(22)	-
Indirect Costs	11,627	-	-	11,627	402	-
Total direct and indirect costs	39,623	-	-	39,623	380	-

3.5 TREC						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	54,255	-	-	19,418	(2,451)	34,837
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,627	-	-	-	-	1,627
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	31,221	-	-	16,872	(122)	14,349
Total direct costs	87,103	-	-	36,291	(2,574)	50,813
Indirect Costs	37,454	-	-	15,605	(1,106)	21,849
Total direct and indirect costs	124,558	-	-	51,895	(3,679)	72,662

4 Information and Outreach

4.1 WITNESS THE ARCTIC NEWSLETTERS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	150,328	22,734	34,201	21,812	16,608	49,725
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	2,446	794	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	196,519	30,414	50,776	24,728	25,372	50,300
Total direct costs	349,294	53,943	84,978	46,540	41,980	100,025
Indirect Costs	147,689	22,642	34,618	19,981	18,082	43,011
Total direct and indirect costs	496,983	76,585	119,596	66,521	60,062	143,035

4.2 INTERNET RESOURCES

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	334,374	52,897	47,674	74,125	(13,330)	87,912
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	10,099	1,740	1,330	7,029	(7,029)	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	28,189	14,102	5,933	8,154	(5,654)	-
Total direct costs	372,661	68,740	54,936	89,307	(26,013)	87,912
Indirect Costs	157,070	28,891	22,302	37,216	(9,999)	37,802
Total direct and indirect costs	529,732	97,631	77,238	126,523	(36,012)	125,714

4.3 ARCTIC INFO LISTSERVER

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	88,302	12,430	10,446	20,013	(5,661)	19,980
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,918	78	1,840	-	2,500	-
Total direct costs	90,220	12,508	12,286	20,013	(3,161)	19,980
Indirect Costs	38,107	5,255	5,031	8,293	(1,047)	8,591
Total direct and indirect costs	128,327	17,763	17,317	28,305	(4,207)	28,571

4.4 DIRECTORY OF ARCTIC RESEARCHERS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	38,355	7,899	5,228	7,769	(2,498)	10,530
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,652	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	17,438	188	12,200	1,550	950	2,500
Total direct costs	57,445	8,087	17,428	9,319	(1,548)	13,030
Indirect Costs	24,178	3,401	7,234	3,820	(478)	5,603
Total direct and indirect costs	81,623	11,489	24,662	13,139	(2,026)	18,633

4.5 INTERNET GRAPHICS ARCHIVE

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	40,979	-	6,966	399	21,363	22,241
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	19,293	-	6,768	25	4,975	5,000
Total direct costs	60,273	-	13,734	424	26,338	27,241
Indirect Costs	25,568	-	5,570	169	11,338	11,714
Total direct and indirect costs	85,840	-	19,304	594	37,676	38,955

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
 OPP-0101279
 NSF Task & Activity Summary

Attachment B

6/18/04 15:43

	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 3 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 4 Budget
4.6 ARCTIC COMMUNITY OUTREACH						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	63,826	13,743	13,784	10,341	4,907	11,475
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	19,293	1,417	-	4,760	1,648	6,508
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	58,763	2,356	9,112	24,665	(16,385)	14,050
Other Direct Costs	<u>102,014</u>	<u>29,356</u>	<u>30,905</u>	<u>10,713</u>	<u>5,307</u>	<u>16,020</u>
Total direct costs	243,897	46,871	53,802	50,480	(4,524)	48,053
Indirect Costs	<u>102,246</u>	<u>19,725</u>	<u>22,295</u>	<u>20,346</u>	<u>(585)</u>	<u>20,663</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>346,143</u></u>	<u><u>66,596</u></u>	<u><u>76,097</u></u>	<u><u>70,826</u></u>	<u><u>(5,108)</u></u>	<u><u>68,716</u></u>

4.7 PUBLICATION: THE ARCTIC						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	32,069	344	55	-	16,042	31,671
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>22,275</u>	<u>275</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>24,000</u>	<u>22,000</u>
Total direct costs	54,344	619	55	-	40,042	53,671
Indirect Costs	<u>23,361</u>	<u>260</u>	<u>23</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>15,068</u>	<u>23,079</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>77,705</u></u>	<u><u>879</u></u>	<u><u>77</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>55,110</u></u>	<u><u>76,750</u></u>

4.8 ENDANGERED SPECIES BULLETIN						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,617	2,150	468	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	2,617	2,150	468	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>1,095</u>	<u>900</u>	<u>196</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>3,712</u></u>	<u><u>3,049</u></u>	<u><u>663</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>

5 Core Support						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	922,271	157,403	145,307	171,239	18,681	207,322
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	76,322	11,770	11,046	17,437	185	17,897
Travel (foreign)	4,919	-	-	-	2,403	2,441
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>412,638</u>	<u>93,425</u>	<u>66,955</u>	<u>87,567</u>	<u>(1,947)</u>	<u>93,845</u>
Total direct costs	1,416,150	262,598	223,309	276,243	19,321	321,505
Indirect Costs	<u>596,820</u>	<u>110,337</u>	<u>90,618</u>	<u>114,646</u>	<u>12,447</u>	<u>138,247</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>2,012,970</u></u>	<u><u>372,935</u></u>	<u><u>313,927</u></u>	<u><u>390,889</u></u>	<u><u>31,768</u></u>	<u><u>459,752</u></u>

TOTAL PROGRAMS						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	3,082,473	495,519	453,064	669,312	54,307	898,813
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	354,859	60,039	58,308	94,814	(12,065)	78,096
Travel (foreign)	4,919	-	-	-	2,403	2,441
Participant Support Costs	799,580	141,933	81,620	212,571	43,263	229,650
Other Direct Costs	<u>1,989,420</u>	<u>364,955</u>	<u>328,314</u>	<u>636,222</u>	<u>(66,814)</u>	<u>473,220</u>
Total direct costs	6,231,250	1,062,446	921,305	1,612,919	21,094	1,682,220
Indirect Costs	<u>2,520,680</u>	<u>446,055</u>	<u>361,968</u>	<u>620,556</u>	<u>56,350</u>	<u>682,585</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>8,751,930</u></u>	<u><u>1,508,501</u></u>	<u><u>1,283,274</u></u>	<u><u>2,233,476</u></u>	<u><u>77,445</u></u>	<u><u>2,364,805</u></u>

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
 OPP-0101279
 NSF Program Summary

Attachment C

6/18/04 15:43

<u>Form 1030 Category</u>		<u>5 Year Cumulative Budget</u>	<u>Year 1 Actuals</u>	<u>Year 2 Actuals</u>	<u>Year 3 Actuals</u>	<u>Year 3 Funds Remaining</u>	<u>Proposed Year 4 Budget</u>
Salaries							
President	A1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Executive director	A2	365,582	67,420	57,768	63,491	17,005	86,112
Other professionals	B2	1,643,327	257,366	242,803	367,586	31,334	497,615
Student	B3	39,408	8,411	11,243	19,755	(9,693)	-
Clerical	B5	251,257	39,702	28,636	50,523	(3,861)	82,060
Total salaries		2,299,574	372,898	340,450	501,354	34,786	665,787
Fringe Benefits	C	782,899	122,621	112,614	167,958	19,522	233,026
Total salaries and fringe benefits		3,082,473	495,519	453,064	669,312	54,307	898,813
Permanent Equipment	D	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	E1	354,859	60,039	58,308	94,814	(12,065)	78,096
Travel (foreign)	E2	4,919	-	-	-	2,403	2,441
Participant Support Costs							
Stipends	F1	33,050	14,800	8,588	(4,938)	6,938	1,600
Travel	F2	381,078	54,779	39,726	101,431	27,405	105,892
Subsistence	F3	385,452	72,354	33,307	116,078	8,920	122,158
Total participant costs		799,580	141,933	81,620	212,571	43,263	229,650
Other Direct Costs							
Materials and supplies	G1	321,404	80,640	55,259	66,565	(6,268)	72,180
Publication cost/ docum/dissem	G2	496,026	63,719	95,442	100,739	38,174	146,861
Consultant services	G3	395,086	111,585	96,791	96,910	4,518	71,800
Computer services	G4	15,269	1,815	11,436	1,018	4,359	500
Subcontracts	G5	247,138	-	30,627	121,698	(61,885)	94,813
Other	G6	514,496	107,196	38,759	249,291	(45,711)	87,066
Total other direct costs		1,989,420	364,955	328,314	636,222	(66,814)	473,220
Total direct costs	H	6,231,250	1,062,446	921,305	1,612,919	21,094	1,682,220
Indirect	I	2,520,680	446,055	361,968	620,556	56,350	682,585
	J	8,751,930	1,508,501	1,283,274	2,233,476	77,445	2,364,805

**SUMMARY
PROPOSAL BUDGET**

YEAR 4 OF 5

4/1/04 to 3/31/05

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.		REVISIED			FOR NSF USE ONLY	
		PROPOSAL NO.: 0101279			DURATION (MONTHS) Proposed Granted	
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR/PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K. Warnick		AWARD NO.				
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and other Senior Associates (List each separately with title; A.7 show number in brackets)		NSF Funded Person-mos.			Funds Requested By	Funds Granted By NSF
		CAL	ACAD	SUMR	Proposer	(If Different)
1.	Wendy K. Warnick , Executive Director	10.8			86,112	
2.						
3.						
4.						
5.						
6.	() OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET EXPLANATION PAGE)					
7.	(1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1-5)				86,112	
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)						
1.	() POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES					
2.	(11) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				497,615	
3.	() GRADUATE STUDENTS					
4.	() UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS					
5.	(2) SECRETARIAL-CLERICAL				82,060	
6.	() OTHER					
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A+B)					665,787	
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					233,026	
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES, AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A+B+C)					898,813	
D. PERMANENT EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$1,000.)						
TOTAL PERMANENT EQUIPMENT						
E. TRAVEL	1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)				78,096	
	2. FOREIGN				2,441	
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS						
	1. STIPENDS \$ 1,600					
	2. TRAVEL 105,892					
	3. SUBSISTENCE 122,158					
	4. OTHER					
110) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS				229,650	
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS						
	1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				72,180	
	2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				146,861	
	3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				71,800	
	4. COMPUTER (ADPE) SERVICES				500	
	5. SUBCONTRACTS				94,813	
	6. OTHER				87,066	
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					473,220	
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					1,682,220	
I. INDIRECT COSTS (SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) 43% on (H) - (D) - (G5)						
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS					682,585	
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H+I)					2,364,805	
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPM 252 AND 253)					77,445	
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					2,287,360	
M. COST SHARING: PROPOSED LEVEL \$		AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$				
PI/PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE *					FOR NSF USE ONLY	
Wendy K. Warnick		18 Jun 04			INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION	
INST. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE		Date Checked		Date of Rate Sheet	Initials-DGC	
Wendy K. Warnick		18 Jun 04				